
Influence of Organization and Leadership on Lecturer Performance

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to determine and analyze the influence of organization and leadership on lecturer performance. Based on the results of the discussion and testing, it can be concluded several things related to this research as follows: Simultaneously the variables of the school committee, organization, and leadership, simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on the performance of Lecturers of the Faculty of Economics, Sisingamangaraja XII University Tapanuli, marked by $F_{count} = 29.324$ and $F_{table} = 2.87$ in this case F_{count} is greater than F_{table} and the significant value is 0.00 less than the alpha value of 0.05. Partially, the school committee variable has no significant effect on the performance of the Lecturer of the Faculty of Economics at Sisingamangaraja XII Tapanuli University which is indicated by the t_{count} value for the school committee variable (1.180) is smaller than $t_{table}(3.18)$ or sig value (0.246) is greater than alpha (0.025). Partially, organizational variables have a positive and significant effect on the performance of Lecturers of the Faculty of Economics, Sisingamangaraja University XII Tapanuli which is indicated by the t_{count} value for the organizational variable (6.096) which is greater than t_{table} (3.18) or the sig value (0.000) is smaller than alpha (0.025).). Partially, the leadership variable has a positive and significant effect on the performance of the Lecturer of the Faculty of Economics, Sisingamangaraja XII Tapanuli University, which is indicated by the t-count value for the leadership variable (4.081) which is greater than t_{table} (3.18) or the sig (0.000) value is smaller than alpha (0.025). The R^2 value obtained is 0.710 or 71.0% which shows the ability of the school committee, organization, and leadership variables in explaining the variations that occur in Lecturer Performance is 71.0%, while the remaining 29.0% is explained by other variables that not included in the model, for example curriculum, lecturer certification, school facilities and others

KEYWORDS: School Committee, Organization, Leadership, Performance

INTRODUCTION

Lecturers as educators are at the forefront of improving the quality of the nation's education, for that the government must be serious and continuously pay attention to various matters relating to the performance of lecturers so that lecturers can play a good role in improving the quality of the nation's education.

To improve the performance of Lecturers of the Faculty of Economics, University of Sisingamangaraja XII Tapanuli, the school carried out many programs and policies and utilized various available resources to improve the performance of Lecturers of the Faculty of Economics Unita, from many factors that could affect the performance of Lecturers. Organization includes reflection and desire, hope and aspiration to achieve an impactful result with work through the way that Lecturers take to produce the best. Organizations in schools are related to hierarchy, job security, openness and closure of schools to the community, work comfort and satisfaction of lecturers and other personnel.

A good organization will provide comfort for lecturers in carrying out their duties in schools with a good climate, the performance of lecturers will increase while a bad organization will certainly interfere with many things in the teaching and learning process and also in other work at school, the climate is not good will make the Lecturer less comfortable working and will certainly result in the low performance of the Lecturer. Likewise, leadership which is the ability to influence is needed in a school so that lecturers can and want to carry out various jobs well, with poor leadership, lecturers will not be able to achieve high performance in school.

From the background and phenomena presented above, the authors try to conduct research by discussing the above variables such as: Organization, leadership, and Lecturer performance, with the research title "Influence, Organization and leadership on the performance of Lecturers of the Faculty of Economics, Sisingamangaraja XII University Tapanuli"

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FORMULATION OF THE PROBLEM

Based on the background described above, the problem is formulated as follows:

1. How is the influence of the Organization on the performance of the Faculty of Economics Unita
2. How is the influence of leadership on the performance of the Lecturer of the Faculty of Economics Unita
3. How is the influence of the school committee, organization and leadership simultaneously on the performance of the Lecturer of the Faculty of Economics Unita

RESEARCH PURPOSES

This study aims to identify and analyze:

1. Knowing and analyzing how the organization's influence on the performance of the Faculty of Economics Unita
2. Knowing and analyzing how the influence of leadership on the performance of the Lecturer of the Faculty of Economics Unita
3. Knowing and analyzing the influence of school committees, organizations and leadership simultaneously on the performance of Lecturers of the Faculty of Economics Unita

LITERATURE REVIEW

Organization

The existence of an organization cannot be separated from the influence of the internal environment of the organization and the influence of the external environment of the organization. Organizations or departments will not be dynamic and develop if the organization is not always open to its environment. Every organization always interacts with each environment, organizational climate internally, or interacts individually with its members. Organizations always want their position to exist in the midst of society. The existence of the vision of the organization or company in carrying out its programs shows that the organization shows the existence of harmony between fellow leaders and their subordinates.

According to Timpe (1993:4), the organization is a series of work environments that can be measured based on the collective and various people who carry out work within the organization and at the same time there is mutual influence between one another with certain goals. Meanwhile, according to Steers (1985: 120) that the organization is the characteristics or characteristics that are felt in the organization, there is a work environment that carries out tasks that tend to influence the behavior of everyone in the organizational environment.

From some of the opinions of these experts that the organization is more focused on the internal environment of the organization. The internal environment in the organization that has variations and various patterns of behavior, culture, attitudes and tendencies of employees or employees in carrying out their duties, as well as the organizational structure greatly affects the behavior and the organization.

Definition of Leadership

Echols and Shadiliy (1996:351) write that leader means leader, leadership means leader, leadership. The use of the term leader which has the meaning of leadership has become part of the terminology in the world of education, especially with regard to the duties and functions of the principal. Leaders and leadership when associated with the principal are the work patterns of someone who has the authority to become the leader of an educational institution. Therefore, discussing the problem of leadership (leadership) as a form of work done, cannot be separated from the discussion and the overall performance of the principal

Wahjosomidjo (2001:17), suggests that, through the communication process, toward the attainment of a specified goal or goals. Furthermore, Nawawi (1989:82), that in leadership the leader factor cannot be separated from the factor of the person being led, both are interdependent so that one cannot exist without the other. Leadership is a process of interaction between the two parties, namely the leader and the led in a human relationship. For this reason, views are often encountered that place the human relationship factor as the core of leadership.

The role of the principal as a leader in educational institutions is an effort that must be able to influence, encourage and mobilize all school members in an effort to achieve common goals.

Leadership is the way or effort of the principal in influencing, encouraging, guiding, directing and mobilizing lecturers, staff, students, parents and other related parties to work / participate in achieving the goals that have been set. In short, how do principals "make" others work to achieve school goals. (Depdikbud, 1999:12).

Understanding Performance

Performance (performance) is the result of work that is concrete, observable, measurable (Irawan, 1997:11). Observable and measurable work results indicate that the work results can be accounted for. According to As'ad (1987:47) performance is the

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level of success of a person in carrying out his job duties. Both understandings emphasize the success of a person in carrying out their duties, but it should not be ignored that human work does not always produce tangible forms. Furthermore, Meiyer (1983:156) says that job performance is a person's success in carrying out work. Success in the implementation of work is a form of one's performance in a job.

RESEARCH METHODS

Research Location and Time

The location or place of research is the Faculty of Economics, University of Sisingamangaraja XII Tapanuli in November 2019

Population and Sample

Population is a group or collection of all elements or individuals who are sources of information in a research. The population in this study were all lecturers of the Faculty of Economics Unita totaling 40 people, and the entire population was sampled in this study or said to be a saturated sample.

Data analysis technique

1. F-Test (Simultaneous Test)
2. T test (Partial Test)
3. Multiple Linear Analysis

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data Descriptive Analysis

The data obtained from the results of descriptive analysis, shows the highest value (maximum), lowest value (minimum), average (mean) and standard deviation of each variable studied for the hypothesis, both independent variables, namely school committee, organization, and leadership. and the dependent variable is the performance of the Unita Faculty of Economics lecturer. The results of the descriptive analysis can be seen in table 1 below:

Table 1. Analysis of Research Description

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Organization	40	13	25	19,95	2,417
Leadership	40	24	45	34,83	3,816
Performance Lecturer	40	28	44	33,73	3,987
Valid N (listwise)	40				

Source: Research Results 2019 (data processed)

From Table 1 above, it can be seen that the average variable X1 (Organization) is 19.95, the highest value is 25 and the lowest value is 13, while the standard deviation is 2.417. The average variable X3 (leadership) is 34.83, the highest value is 45 and the lowest value is 24, while the standard deviation is 3.816. The average variable Y (Lecturer Performance) is 33.73, the highest value is 44 and the lowest value is 28, while the standard deviation is 3.987.

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

The coefficient of determination aims to measure how far the model's ability, namely the variation of the independent variables, namely the school committee, organization, and leadership in explaining the variation of the dependent variable, namely the performance of the Lecturer of the Faculty of Economics Unita. The value of the coefficient of determination R² can be seen in Table 2:

Table 2. Coefficient of Determinants (R² Test)

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	,842 ^a	,710	,685	2,236	2,708

a. Predictors: (Constant), Principal Leadership, School Committee, Organizational Climate

b. Dependent Variable: Lecturer Performance

Source: Research Results, 2019 (data processed)

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The R2 value obtained is 0.710 or 71.0% which indicates the ability of the school committee, organization, and leadership variables in explaining the variations that occur in Lecturer Performance is 71.0%, while the remaining 29.0% is explained by other variables that are not included in the model for example curriculum, lecturer certification, school facilities and others.

Simultaneous Test (F Test)

To test this hypothesis, F statistic is used with decision criteria. If the value of Fcount is greater than Ftable, then H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted. Based on Table 3 below, it can be seen that Fcount = 29.324 and Ftable = 2.87 in this case Fcount is greater than Ftable and the significant value is 0.00 less than the alpha value of 0.05, so the decision taken is H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted. The acceptance of the alternative hypothesis shows that the independent variables of the school committee, organization, and leadership are able to explain the diversity of the dependent variable, namely the Performance of the Lecturer of the Faculty of Economics Unita (Y), so in this case the variables of the school committee, organization, and leadership simultaneously have a significant effect on the performance of the Lecturer of the Faculty of Economics Unita.

Table 3. Simultaneous Test (F Test)

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	439,943	3	146,648	29,324	,000 ^b
Residual	180,032	36	5,001		
Total	619,975	39			

Dependent Variable: Lecturer Performance

Predictors: (Constant), Principal Leadership, School Committee, Organizational Climate

Source: Research Results, (processed data)

Partial Test (t Test)

Partial testing was carried out in two directions, using an alpha significance level of 2.5%. Hypothesis testing is done by comparing the value of tcount with the value of ttable with the decision criteria are:

If tcount < ttable H0 is accepted or H1 is rejected

If tcount > ttable H0 is rejected or H1 is accepted

Based on Table 4, it can be seen that the constant value is 2.322 and the coefficient value of each variable is 0.101 for X1 and 0.416 for X2. Then the regression model for this research is as follows:

$$Y = 2.322 + 0.986X_1 + 0.416X_2$$

Where :

Y = Lecturer Performance

X1 = Organization

X2 = Leadership

Table 4. Partial Test (t Test)

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	2,322	4,106		,566	,575
Organization	,986	,162	,598	6,096	,000
Leadership	,416	,102	,398	4,081	,000

Source: Research Results, 2015 (processed data)

From Table 4. above, the following results are obtained:

1. The value of tcount for the Organization variable (6.096) is greater than ttable (3.18) or the value of sig (0.000) is smaller than alpha (0.025). Based on the results obtained, Ho is rejected and H1 is accepted for the Organization variable. These results explain that partially the Organization has a positive and significant effect on the performance of the Unita Faculty of

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Economics lecturers, or in other words that the Unita Faculty of Economics Organizations have a strong role in improving the performance of the lecturers, or in influencing the performance of the lecturers.

2. The tcount value for the leadership variable (4.081) is greater than ttable (3.18) or the sig value (0.000) is smaller than alpha (0.025). Based on the results obtained, Ho is rejected and H1 is accepted for the leadership variable, then partially leadership has a positive and significant influence on the performance of Lecturers of the Faculty of Economics, Sisingamangaraja XII Tapanuli University or in other words that leadership has a strong role in improving or influencing the performance of Lecturers of the Faculty of Economics. Unita.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the discussion and testing in the previous chapter, it can be concluded several things related to this research as follows:

1. Simultaneously Organization and leadership, simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on the performance of Lecturers of the Faculty of Economics, Sisingamangaraja University XII Tapanuli, marked by Fcount = 29.324 and Ftable = 2.87 in this case Fcount is greater than Ftable and the significant value is 0.00 less than alpha value 0.05
2. Partially, organizational variables have a positive and significant effect on the performance of Lecturers of the Faculty of Economics, Sisingamangaraja University XII Tapanuli which is indicated by the tcount value for the organizational variable (6.096) which is greater than ttable (3.18) or the sig value (0.000) is smaller than alpha (0.025).
3. Partially the leadership variable has a positive and significant effect on the performance of Lecturers of the Faculty of Economics, Sisingamangaraja University XII Tapanuli, indicated by the t-value for the leadership variable (4.081) greater than ttable (3.18) or the sig (0.000) value smaller than alpha (0.025).
4. The R2 value obtained is 0.710 or 71.0% which shows the ability of the school committee, organization, and leadership variables in explaining the variations that occur in Lecturer Performance is 71.0%, while the remaining 29.0% is explained by other variables that not included in the model, for example curriculum, lecturer certification, school facilities and others

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